

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF COMMUNITY SAFETY ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE CRIME PREVENTION AND RESIDENTS' SATISFACTION

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The Mediating Effect of Community Safety on the Relationship Between the Crime Prevention and Residents' Satisfaction

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the mediating effect of community safety on the relationship between crime prevention and residents' satisfaction. The descriptive non-experimental quantitative design utilizing descriptive correlational technique was employed in this study. In selecting the respondents, random sampling was used, thus, 150 respondents were randomly selected from 10 different barangays in the City of Tacurong. Based on the results of the study, the extent of crime prevention was always in terms of crime prevention through social development, while seldom in community crime prevention, situational crime prevention, and developmental crime prevention. The level of resident's satisfaction was very high in terms of quality of service, police-community relation, police performance, and victimization. The extent of community safety was always on police investigation in the City of Tacurong. On the other hand, there was a significant relationship between crime prevention and community safety, resident's satisfaction and community safety, and resident satisfaction and crime prevention. Furthermore, there was a direct effect of crime prevention and residents' satisfaction, crime prevention and community safety, and residents' satisfaction on police investigations. The study implied that community safety plays a significant mediating role in influencing the relationship between crime prevention efforts and residents' satisfaction.

Keywords: *criminal justice education, community safety, crime prevention, resident's satisfaction, mediation*

Introduction

The happiness of local residents is a significant issue that impacts people's health and quality of life in communities worldwide. It includes various elements that residents encounter in their living spaces, such as fulfillment, happiness, and contentment. Due to its direct effects on community development, social cohesiveness, individual well-being, investment, and resident appeal, this problem is of utmost importance. A multifaceted strategy comprising cooperation between governments, legislators, urban planners, and community organizations must address this global issue adequately. Evidence-based approaches, resident feedback, and research are essential for comprehending the requirements of various communities (Kang, 2020; Merenda et al., 2021).

Additionally, residence satisfaction is paramount due to its significant impact on community well-being, social cohesion, community development, attractiveness for residents and businesses, civic engagement, and a positive community image. Setting home happiness as a top priority results in happier people, more robust social networks, economic development, enhanced community vitality, engaged civic engagement, and a favorable reputation for the community. Communities can build conditions that promote well-being, social peace, and high quality of life for their citizens by strongly emphasizing resident satisfaction (Circo et al., 2019).

Unfortunately, community safety in the Philippines is contingent upon the cooperation of law enforcement agencies, such as the PNP, in implementing crime prevention techniques and the contentment of the populace with the degree of safety and security provided. Maintaining citizens' contentment with their neighborhood's general safety and well-being is feasible while creating a safer environment by implementing a community-oriented policing approach, encouraging trust and collaboration, and raising public knowledge. People can actively contribute to their safety and take part in crime prevention activities by arming themselves with information about safety precautions, crime reporting protocols, and community involvement programs (Milton, 2018; Telep & Hibdon, 2018).

On the other hand, crime prevention and residents' satisfaction are substantial; notable research gaps require further exploration. One area of focus should be examining how contextual factors influence the relationship between crime prevention and residents' satisfaction across diverse cultural, social, and economic contexts. Understanding these nuances can inform the development of tailored strategies and interventions. Additionally, research should delve into practical approaches for community engagement in crime prevention efforts. Investigating the role of community participation, citizen involvement, and social networks can provide valuable insights into fostering collaborative approaches to community safety. Furthermore, there is a need to explore the long-term effects of crime prevention strategies on residents' satisfaction and community safety.

The constant change of guard at the Philippine National Police has done more harm than good to the institution. On the other hand, there are few positive responses from the people to the Philippine National Police's services. The researcher is interested in and aimed to know community safety satisfaction and the relationship between crime prevention and residents' satisfaction. The researcher decided to conduct this study to gain knowledge and evaluate the effect of community safety on the relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction.

Research Objectives

The study aimed to determine the mediating effect of community safety on the relationship between crime prevention and residents'

satisfaction. Specifically, this study sought to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the extent of crime prevention in terms of
 - 1.1. community crime prevention;
 - 1.2. situational crime prevention;
 - 1.3. developmental crime prevention; and
 - 1.4. crime prevention through social development.
2. To ascertain the level of residents' satisfaction in terms of:
 - 2.1. quality of police strategy;
 - 2.2. police community relation;
 - 2.3. police ratings; and
 - 2.4. victimization.
3. To measure the extent of community safety in terms of:
 - 3.1. community policing;
 - 3.2. social capital; and
 - 3.3. perception of safety
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. crime prevention and residents' satisfaction;
 - 4.2. crime prevention and community safety; and
 - 4.3. community safety and residents' satisfaction.
5. To determine the significance of community safety mediation in the relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative nonexperimental research design using a descriptive correlational technique. Path analysis was employed to treat the mediating variable.

Nonexperimental research lacks the manipulation of an independent variable, random assignment of respondents to conditions or orders of conditions, or both. There are many ways in which nonexperimental research can be preferred. Rather than focusing on the statistical relationship between two variables, the research question or hypothesis may address a single variable. A statistical link between variables that is not causative can be the subject of the research question. A causal relationship may be the subject of the research question. However, the independent variable cannot be changed, and respondents cannot be randomly assigned to conditions or orders of conditions. The research question can be broad, exploratory, or about having a particular experience (Bloomfield & Fisher, 2019).

When conducting correlational research, the researcher measures the two variables of interest and evaluates the relationship between them with little to no effort to adjust for other factors. Correlational research is carried out by a research technique student who determines whether several middle school pupils have been bullied and then assesses each student's self-esteem. A correlational study is a research design that looks at the connections between two or more variables. With correlational research, a nonexperimental research technique, two variables are measured, and the statistical relationship between them is understood and assessed independently of any other variable. No variables are altered or under the experimenter's control since correlational investigations are nonexperimental (Seeram, 2019).

On the other hand, mediation analysis is always of concern. With causal relations between variables. In complete mediation, the independent Variable (X) causes the mediator (M), and M, in turn, causes the dependent variable (Y). In partial mediation, there are both direct and indirect effects of X on Y. There is growing interest in studying mediation as a research topic due to the importance of doing so for theoretical accounts of causal mechanisms and the strict guidelines associated with research design when dealing with cause-effect relationships (in which the mediator provides an explanatory account). Many designs concentrate on mediators, including nonexperimental (cross-sectional or longitudinal) and experimental. Conceptual elements are crucial for differentiating between intervening variables, such as mediators, moderators, and confounding variables, regardless of the study design (Mehmetoglu, 2018).

Respondents

This study's respondents comprised 150 individuals selected from 10 different barangays in the City of Tacurong. The distribution included 19 respondents from Buenaflor, 16 from Baras, 12 from San Antonio, 16 from D'Lesma, 12 from Griño, 15 from Tina, 18 from San Rafael, 17 from San Emmanuel, 14 from San Pablo, and 10 from Lancheta. After applying Slovin's Formula, a final sample of 150 respondents from an initial pool of 238 was used to determine the appropriate sample size. The study focused on the entire city of Tacurong, with specific considerations for the number of police officers selected per station (Anugraheni et al., 2023).

The researcher applied Slovin's Formula to collect data for this study, explicitly targeting residents of Tacurong City from its ten barangays. To ensure a representative sample, inclusion criteria were established: respondents had to be male or female, residents of

Tacurong City for at least ten years, aged between 23 and 60, and easily approachable.

In adherence to the inclusion criteria, the study excluded individuals under 23 and those over 60 years of age. Furthermore, respondents who were unwilling or unable to consent or participate in data collection were also excluded. Throughout the study, respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any point without consequence. Emphasizing this right ensured that participants were fully aware of their autonomy and could withdraw without providing a reason.

Table 1. *The Distribution of the Respondents*

Barangay	Number of Respondents	
	N	N
Buenaflor	30	19
Baras	25	16
San. Antonio	20	12
D'Ledesma	25	16
Griño	20	12
Tina	24	15
San Rafael	28	18
San Emmanuel	27	17
San Pablo	23	14
Lancheta	16	10
TOTAL	238	150

Instrument

The instrument of this study was a research-made questionnaire. The researcher prepared a structured survey questionnaire checklist that sufficiently provided the information needed in the study. Part I of the survey questionnaire consisted of 20 items on crime prevention, Part II consisted of 20 items on residents' satisfaction with police operations in the City of Tacurong, and Part III consisted of 10 items on community safety.

Rating scale on the Extent of Crime Prevention and Community Safety

Numeric Scale	Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
1	1.00 – 1.79	Never	This means that the extent of crime prevention and community safety is Not Manifested at All
2	1.80 – 2.59	Seldom	This means that the extent of crime prevention and community safety is Manifested in Few Instances
3	2.60 – 3.39	Sometime	This means that the extent of crime prevention and community safety is Manifested Occasionally
4	3.40 – 4.19	often	This means that the extent of crime prevention and community safety is Most of The Time
5	4.20 – 5.00	Always	This means that the extent of crime prevention and community safety is Manifested All the Time.

Rating scale on the Level of Residents' Satisfaction

Numeric Scale	Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	This means that the level of residents' satisfaction is Not Evident
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree	This means that the level of residents' satisfaction is Evident
3	2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Agree	This means that the level of residents' satisfaction is Evident
4	3.40 – 4.19	Agree	This means that the level of residents' satisfaction is Highly Evident
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	This means that the level of residents' satisfaction is Very Highly Evident

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Internal Consistency

Cronbach's Alpha	Internal Consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$	Good
$0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$	Acceptable
$0.7 > \alpha \geq 0.6$	Questionable
$0.6 > \alpha \geq 0.5$	Poor
$0.5 > \alpha$	Unacceptable

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha Internal Consistency

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	Number of Items
.922	.8849	50

According to the data, Cronbach's alpha for internal consistency was outstanding, with $\alpha = .922$. The researcher can reliably assess the degree of crime prevention, resident satisfaction, and community safety using the survey questions.

Procedure

The data collection process for this study followed a systematic procedure. Initially, the researcher obtained the necessary permissions by sending letters of authorization to the Ethics Review Committee (ERC), the Dean of the relevant institution, and the Philippine National Police Region XII Regional Director, PBGEN Alexander Camelon Tagum. Additionally, the researcher addressed a separate letter to the ten barangays in the study to seek their approval to conduct the research.

After receiving the necessary approvals, the researcher administered an Informed Consent Form (ICF) and a survey questionnaire to 150 respondents in Tacurong City, Philippines, on December 13, 2022. The researcher personally visited the different barangays and distributed the questionnaires to the respondents. The questionnaires were collected one week after the distribution to ensure respondents had sufficient time to answer the questions.

Significantly, the researcher successfully retrieved all the distributed questionnaires containing the responses. Subsequently, the researcher carefully reviewed the collected responses to ensure completeness and accuracy. The data was then compiled and organized for further analysis and interpretation, aligning with the study's objectives. By following this systematic process, the intention was to guarantee the trustworthiness and credibility of the gathered data. These meticulous steps facilitated a thorough analysis and interpretation of the data, ultimately enhancing the overall integrity and quality of the findings in the study.

Data Analysis

The collected data were collated, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools. The following tools were employed in this study:

Mean. This tool determined the extent of crime prevention, community safety, and residents' satisfaction.

In answer to objective 4, Pearson-r was utilized to determine the significant relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction, crime prevention and community safety, and community safety and resident satisfaction.

Path Analysis demonstrated the mediation between the two and strengthened the obtained result. A statistical method called path analysis enables users to look at effect patterns within a system of variables. It is one of several types of the general linear model that examine the relationship between several dependent variables and a collection of predictor factors. Path analysis is similar to various regression in that the effect of numerous predictors on a criterion variable can be assessed.

Ethical Considerations

A primary ethical consideration had distinct implications for this quantitative research. These issues and concerns might come from the methodology used in this study. The ethical challenges applicable to this research concern are the issues of the proper operation of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. This study followed the standards of the RMMC Ethics and Review Committee for the guidelines of ethical consideration, especially when dealing with the data and population such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were given the choice to take part without any plans for loss of benefits or compensation in the event of consequences. As a result, the respondents' rights to add to the corpus of knowledge were thoughtfully analyzed and anticipated once the goal and advantages of the study were explained to them. The participants in this study were not coerced into taking part.

Privacy and confidentiality. By the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards the fundamental human right to privacy, respondents had the right to privacy, which should not be infringed upon without their informed agreement. In this quantitative study, one approach

to maintain privacy and secrecy was to provide respondents with the choice to withhold their names from the Survey. Additionally, anonymity and secrecy are achieved by not disclosing the informants' age, gender, job title, vocation, and, if applicable, any illnesses. For security reasons, their identification was thus kept private.

The informed consent process. The prospective research respondents were fully informed about the research's objectives, methods, and benefits as comprehensively as possible within the framework of the study. The respondents' consent was obtained, indicating their participation was asked voluntarily. This was done in written form, stating all the essential details to be disclosed to the respondents and how the Survey was conducted. The respondents were asked to affix their signatures to the informed consent form confirming that they voluntarily agreed to participate in the survey. Since the respondents are consenting adults, asking for parents' consent was unnecessary. The names of the respondents did not appear in the survey questionnaire, and their answers were kept confidential. The respondents knew they could withdraw from participating in the study at any time.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. In order to enable the respondents to draw conclusions from the researcher and grasp the core of the study, the researcher explained the survey's goal. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the significance and the reasoning behind the study.

Risks. Only when there was a reasonable favorable benefit-risk ratio was research done. It was equally crucial in this investigation to safeguard the participants from serious injury. The welfare of the respondents was prioritized. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed as their identity was confidential. Their security and safety were of utmost concern. As the researcher, it was ensured that the respondents were emotionally, socially, and physically prepared. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher ensured the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. This study may benefited the respondents as the results could serve as an eye-opener for PNP officials, police officers, and junior police officers, providing insights on creating programs and improving their work in the community to increase efficiency and make them competent public servants. The study was conducted with a clear purpose: to serve its internal and external stakeholders, especially the residents. Furthermore, to ensure the research's benefits, the researcher took all necessary precautions to avoid harming the respondents' lives and promote further undertakings in related studies.

Plagiarism. The study was run via plagiarism detection tools such as Grammarly, and it had no traces or indications of misinterpreting someone else's work. To be a researcher, one needs moral traits and ideals that are linked to positive character and integrity. The researcher needs to be more knowledgeable about the concept of plagiarism to produce a respectable research report.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not indicate overclaiming or exaggerating, nor did it hint at deliberately distorting the theoretical expectation. Furthermore, it had to follow stricter guidelines regarding data manipulation, which included making claims, omitting crucial information, and using supplies, equipment, or techniques that would deceive others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). The study lacked any indication of a conflict of interest, such as the disclosure of conflicts of interest (COIs), which are a set of circumstances in which a secondary interest—such as financial or academic gains or recognitions—tends to influence professional judgment regarding a primary interest, such as the welfare of respondents or the validity of the research. In addition, the respondents were coerced into participating in the survey by the researcher, who had no authority or influence over them.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the respondents about any possible danger. Any study must humbly protect the respondents' rights, source, and appropriate principles.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to protocol. After the panelists, adviser, and committee of the RMMCERC gave their approval, the researcher sent a formal letter to the Tacurong City Police Station Chief of Police. Region XII, requesting permission to conduct the study.

Authorship. The study's researcher is a current student at the RMMC Graduate School. His adviser guided him throughout the production of this work, and he made several adjustments to his thesis based on his ideas. Because of his guidance, the paper was refined. Additionally, the researcher adhered to the RMMC Ethics Review Committee's guidelines for ethical consideration.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation and interpretation of the data gathered in the study.

The Extent of Crime Prevention

The first objective of this study was to determine the extent of crime prevention while the community evaluated it. The extent of crime prevention was expressed in terms of community crime prevention, developmental crime prevention, and crime prevention through social development.

Table 4 presents the data on the extent of crime prevention in police operations in the City of Tacurong. The extent of crime prevention garnered an overall mean score of 4.2, indicating that it was manifested in a few instances. This means that the extent of crime prevention was experienced in the community and should be implemented and improved for better crime prevention.

Data revealed that crime prevention through social development had the highest mean score of 4.4, indicating that the community always manifested crime prevention. Also, community crime prevention received a total mean score of 4.1, meaning that the community experienced crime prevention most of the time. In addition, situational crime prevention with a total mean score of 4.1, indicated that the community experienced crime prevention most of the time. Further, developmental crime prevention got a total mean score of 4.1, meaning the community experienced crime prevention most of the time.

Table 4. *The Extent of Crime Prevention*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Community Crime Prevention	4.1	Often
Situational Crime Prevention	4.1	Often
Developmental Crime Prevention	4.1	Often
Crime Prevention through Social Development	4.4	Always

The Level of Resident's Satisfaction

The second objective of this study was the level of residents' satisfaction as evaluated by the community. The residents' satisfaction was expressed regarding the quality of services, police-community relations, police performance, and victimization.

Table 5 presents residents' satisfaction with police operations in the City of Tacurong. The satisfaction level reached an overall mean of 4.2, indicating that it was highly evident in the community.

Data revealed that police-community relations garnered the highest mean score of 4.4, signifying that residents' satisfaction was highly evident in the community. Also, the quality of services gathered a total mean score of 4.2, indicating that residents' satisfaction was very highly evident in the community. In addition, police performance received a total mean score of 4.2, signifying that residents' satisfaction was very highly evident in the community. Further, victimization with the lowest total mean score of 4.1, meant residents' satisfaction was highly evident in the community.

Table 5. *The Level of Resident's Satisfaction*

Indicators	Mean	Description
Quality of Service	4.2	Strongly Agree
Police Community Relation	4.4	Strongly Agree
Police Performance	4.2	Strongly Agree
Victimization	4.1	Agree

The Extent of Community Safety

Table 6 presents the third objective of the study, the extent of community safety as evaluated by the community. The extent of community safety garnered an overall mean score of 4.3, indicating always. This means the community is safer than before, with residents consistently expressing this belief. The visible presence of the police gave people a sense of security, and residents are generally satisfied with the police's efforts in preventing crimes. The city is perceived as safe, recommended to tourists, and considered free from crimes and threats. The police officers were perceived as highly competent, demonstrating proficiency in knowing when and how to employ force appropriately. Moreover, they consistently treated citizens with respect and dignity, fostering a positive and respectful atmosphere. Their proactive and responsive presence in times of need further strengthened community-police relations. Additionally, their friendly demeanor played a crucial role in building and sustaining positive interactions within the community.

Table 6. *The Extent of Community Safety*

	Indicators	Mean	Description
1	The community is safer than years ago.	4.3	Always
2	The visibility of the police assures everyone that they feel safe in the community.	4.0	Often
3	I am satisfied with the performance of the police officers in preventing crimes in the city.	4.1	Often
4	Tacurong is a crime and threat-free city.	4.0	Often
5	I recommend that tourists visit our city since it is safe.	4.0	Often
6	Police officers have the authority to determine when to use force. It is within the authority of police personnel to determine when to use force.	4.1	Often
7	The police officers know how much force to use to protect the citizens.	4.1	Often
8	The police officers in our area treat citizens with dignity and respect.	4.3	Always
9	The police officers in our area are present when one needs them.	4.2	Always
10	The police officers in our area are friendly.	4.2	Always
	TOTAL	4.3	Always

Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Resident Satisfaction

Table 7 presents the data for this sub-problem. Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to treat the data gathered.

The analysis of the relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction revealed significant findings. When tested at an alpha level of 0.05 with 148 degrees of freedom, the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was determined to be 0.748. This computed value substantially exceeded the critical tabular value of 0.163, indicating a strong positive correlation between crime prevention and resident satisfaction. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, which suggests no significant relationship between these variables. These results provide compelling evidence that resident satisfaction significantly influences crime prevention efforts, particularly in the context of police investigations.

This implies that communities with higher resident satisfaction levels tend to have more effective crime prevention measures, notably concerning police investigations. The positive correlation suggests that as resident satisfaction increases, so does the effectiveness of crime prevention efforts, particularly those related to police activities. This underscores the importance of considering resident perceptions and attitudes when designing and implementing crime prevention strategies.

Table 7. *Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Residents' Satisfaction*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value n=150		Decision a= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
<i>Crime Prevention Vs Residents' Satisfaction</i>	148	0.748	.163	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.

Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Community Safety

Table 8 shows the significant relationship between crime prevention and community safety. Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to treat the data gathered.

Analyzing the relationship between crime prevention and community safety yielded significant findings. When tested at an alpha level of 0.05 with 148 degrees of freedom, the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was 0.603. This computed value exceeded the critical tabular value of 0.138, indicating a substantial positive correlation between crime prevention and community safety. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected, posing no significant relationship between these variables. These results provide compelling evidence that the level of crime prevention significantly influences community safety, particularly regarding police investigations.

This suggests that communities with more robust crime prevention measures tend to experience higher levels of safety, particularly in the context of police investigations. The positive correlation implies that as crime prevention efforts increase, community safety, particularly in police investigations, also improves. This underscores the importance of investing in crime prevention strategies to enhance overall community safety and bolster the effectiveness of law enforcement.

Table 8. *Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Community Safety*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value n=150		Decision α= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Crime Prevention Vs Community Safety	148	0.603	0.138	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.

Significant Relationship between Community Safety and Residents’ Satisfaction

Table 9 presents the data for this sub-problem. Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to treat the data gathered.

Analyzing the relationship between community safety and resident satisfaction yielded significant results. When tested at an alpha level of 0.05 with 148 degrees of freedom, the computed Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was found to be 0.657. This value exceeded the critical tabular value of 0.163, indicating a strong positive correlation between community safety and resident satisfaction. As a result, the null hypothesis, which posits no significant relationship between these variables, was rejected. These findings prove that community safety significantly influences residents' satisfaction, particularly regarding police investigations.

This implies that communities characterized by higher levels of safety tend to have more satisfied residents, particularly in their perceptions of police effectiveness. The positive correlation suggests that as community safety improves, residents' satisfaction with police investigations also increases. This underscores the importance of prioritizing efforts to enhance community safety, as it contributes to residents' overall well-being and sense of security and positively impacts their perceptions of law enforcement effectiveness.

Table 9. *Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Residents’ Satisfaction*

Variables	Df	r _{xy} value n=150		Decision α= 0.05	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
Community Safety Vs Resident Satisfaction	148	0.657	.163	Reject null hypothesis	There is a significant relationship.

The Significance of the Mediation of Community Safety on the Relationship between Crime Prevention and Resident’s Satisfaction

Table 10 shows the path analysis of the mediating effect of community safety on the relationship between crime prevention and residents' satisfaction with police investigations.

The data revealed the direct effect of crime prevention and residents’ satisfaction, crime prevention and community safety, and community safety and resident’s satisfaction on police investigations. Crime prevention and community safety were the paths with an unstandardized regression coefficient of .887, standardized regression coefficient of .802, S.E. of .034, and a probability value of less than 0.05. Below the significance level of 0.05 implies that these two variables have a significant relationship, and a low or small standard error means that the estimate is more precise. The influence of efficiency, or effect size, is 97%, which is significant enough to reject the null hypothesis. The unstandardized regression coefficient for the route b coefficient—crime prevention and community safety—is also.895, whereas the standardized regression coefficient is.854, S.E. of.042 and a p-value of.018, both of which are below the 0.05 significant alpha threshold. Consequently, there was a substantial correlation between achievements and efficiency. Competence and achievements have a 10% impact size.

Moreover, the path c coefficient shows the effect size of community safety and resident satisfaction. The data result has an unstandardized regression coefficient of .996 or 74% efficiency, a standardized regression coefficient of .946, a computed standard error of .044, and a p-value smaller than 0.05. This means that the two variables have a significant relationship. Mathematically, this supports the assumption that crime prevention is associated with residents’ satisfaction.

In conclusion, the study's analysis revealed significant and robust relationships between crime prevention, community safety, and resident satisfaction, emphasizing their direct impact on police investigations. The statistical results confirmed the relevance of these linkages, as evidenced by low standard errors and p-values below 0.05. The study demonstrates the significant impact size, namely a notable 97% for the association between community safety and crime prevention, which results in the null hypothesis being rejected. The study also emphasizes the significance of efficiency in preventing crime, with a 10% effect size on competence and achievements.

Table 10. Mediating Effect: Direct Analysis

PATH	ESTIMATES		SE	C.R.	P
	Unstandar dized	Standard ized			
Crime Prevention → Residents' Satisfaction	.887	.802	.034	25.34	***
Crime Prevention → Community Safety	.895	.854	.042	2.350	.018
Community Safety → Residents' Satisfaction	.996	.946	.044	15.600	***

Furthermore, the outcome of the mediating effect calculation is shown in Figure 1. The effect size of the three variables' path correlation coefficients employed in this investigation is displayed. The route analysis produced a significant p-value of less than 0.05 at the 0.05 level. It suggests that community safety substantially affected the relationship between crime prevention and resident's satisfaction with police investigations. The causative relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction was also reduced by a significant beta coefficient value of 667 to 64, which was still strong, following community safety, is the mediator variable.

In addition, a third variable cannot function as a mediator unless three conditions are satisfied (Baron & Kenny, 1986). These were classified as Steps 1 through 3 in Table 7. The last step is step 4. Step 1 (Path c): The dependent variable (resident satisfaction) is strongly predicted by crime prevention as the independent variable (IV) (DV). Crime prevention (IV) in step 2 (Path a) primarily refers to community safety, the mediator (MV). Community safety (MV) significantly impacts residents' happiness in step 3 (Path b). Similarly, the first three phases seek to demonstrate that there are zero-order correlations between the variables.

Figure 3. Regression Weights on the Mediating Effect of Community Safety on the Relationship between Crime Prevention and Resident's Satisfaction

Furthermore, based only on relationship estimation, we can immediately assume that mediation was not likely without any relationship factors. Moreover, step 4 must be followed if there is a substantial correlation between steps 1 and 3. The combined impact of resident happiness and crime prevention was substantial in step 4.

To determine the relevance of the intervening variable, additional route analysis of the mediation effect using AMOS was necessary as

a matter of triangulation. Furthermore, complete mediation is attained if the IV's effect on the DV ceases to be significant at the end of the study. This indicates that the mediating variable mediated every effect. Only partial mediation was found if the regression coefficient was significantly lower but still significant at the end. \\This indicates that while specific components were either direct or mediated by variables not included in the model, the MV mediates a portion of the IV. In this instance, MV (community management) control significantly reduced the impact of IV (crime prevention) on DV (resident satisfaction).

In conclusion, this study unveiled the significant mediating role of community safety in the relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction with police investigations. Through route analysis and adherence to mediation steps, the study established that community safety substantially influenced the connection between crime prevention and resident satisfaction. Despite a slight reduction in the association after accounting for community safety, the overall impact remained noteworthy. The findings emphasized the importance of considering community safety as a critical factor in shaping public perceptions and satisfaction with law enforcement efforts

The Extent of Crime Prevention. The extent of crime prevention in police investigations in the City of Tacurong is always in crime prevention through social development, while it is seldom in community crime prevention, situational crime prevention, or developmental crime prevention.

Crime prevention through social development indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondent, as manifested all the time. It means that the police officers assisting citizens in need is just as important as enforcing the law, law enforcement should be seen primarily as a service-oriented profession rather than a crime control profession, and lowering citizens' fear of crime should be just as high a priority as cutting the crime rate, crimes are only one of several problems about which the police officers should be concerned, and the police officers may ask the residents the type of services they wish.

This assumption parallels the study of Lee and Cho (2018) who stated that poverty and crime frequently coexist. However, studies show that inequality, not poverty, is the driving force behind crime. Countries with high levels of overall poverty do not necessarily have higher levels of crime. Significant crime rates are usually correlated with considerable income inequality. Lessened after managing MV (community safety), a breakdown in societal norms and values is another driver of crime. Unemployment, low education, broken families, few opportunities, and isolation from the formal economy worsened this breakdown. The effect was still strong; therefore, only partial mediation occurred.

Often, community crime prevention indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondent, as manifested occasionally. It means that the community has a neighborhood crime watch program, police officer's protection in our community has increased over the past three years, there is the visibility of police patrols in the community, residents are actively involved in community crime prevention, and there is a feeling of safety in our community.

This assumption parallels the study of Oh et al., (2019), which stated that a review of over four decades of evaluation research shows that situational prevention initiatives effectively reduce crime's harms. Individual case studies and comprehensive reviews of evaluation studies provide evidence of SCP techniques' effectiveness. Various classification schemes and methodologies were used in these reviews. Some have concluded from each study, others have organized findings by location or intervention type, and others have investigated the most common SCP techniques, such as CCTV and street lighting.

Often situational, crime prevention indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondent as agreed. It means that the residents do not go out after dark because of the possibility of crime against them, there is an improvement in the street lighting in the city, the police officers cooperate with the public to address their concerns, the police officers provide information to the public on ways to reduce crime, and the police officers have been treating the residence fairly.

This assumption parallels the study of Cai et al. (2020), who stated that crime prevention models can encompass various approaches, including technology-oriented strategies and punitive, corrective, and mechanical methods. These models can also be target-oriented, focusing on specific groups or areas, and stage-oriented, addressing prevention during the intention, preparation, and attempt stages of criminal activity. By considering a combination of these approaches, crime prevention efforts can be more comprehensive and effective in addressing different aspects of criminal behavior.

An often-developmental crime prevention indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondent, as manifested occasionally. It means that the law enforcement was doing an excellent job of protecting me in my community over the past three years, believed that crime in my community has been minimized, the police officers were active in participating in training in preventing crimes in the locality, there was alertness to the police officers in terms of crime prevention, and police officers were active in information dissemination in the community. This presumption is consistent with Zheng's (2020) research, which found that preventing, controlling, eliminating, and reducing crime entails modifying the social and physical contexts before, during, and following criminal activity. Criminology takes an etiological and environmental approach to crime.

The Level of Resident's Satisfaction. The level of resident satisfaction with police investigations in the City of Tacurong was very high in terms of quality of service, police-community relations, and police performance, while high in terms of victimization.

A very highly evident quality of service indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondents. It means

that the police officers showed professionalism, the police officers in the city are trustworthy, the police officers are knowledgeable about their duties and responsibilities, the police officers are accountable for their actions, and the police officers always carried fairness.

A very evident police-community relationship indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondents. It means that the police officers are approachable, know the people who live in the neighborhood, neighborhoods are active with the crime prevention programs of the local government unit. The neighborhood and police officers in the area have a good relationship. The neighborhood has concerns about police officers' duties and responsibilities.

This assumption parallels the study of Arble et al. (2019), who stated that police legitimacy can foster voluntary cooperation with authorities and a willingness to solve community problems. Along with citizens' perceived obligation to obey, public trust in police actions, policies, and performance is essential to police legitimacy. Measures of confidence and satisfaction reflect a positive attitude toward authority, which prepares citizens to act according to the authority's instructions.

A very highly evident police performance indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondents. It means that the police officers were carefully behaving in public, continuously protecting the community, satisfied with the treatment received during the most recent contact with the police activities, doing their job, taking appropriate action every time, and being efficient.

This assumption parallels the study of Putrik et al. (2019), who stated that living in unsafe neighborhoods has been linked to poor mental and physical health, as well as lower resident well-being. Crime, but also fear of crime and general feelings of safety, have been linked to poor self-perceptions of health, higher levels of stress, more depressive symptoms, poor mental health, an increased risk of coronary heart disease, less physical activity, and even adverse birth outcomes. According to a recent study conducted in New Zealand, pregnant women who lived in a hazardous environment had high levels of stress hormones called cortisol and low self-rated health, which may have an impact on the health of both the mother and the unborn child. Unsafe sensations function as a mediator between low socioeconomic position and poor self-rated health, according to another American study.

A very highly evident victimization indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and done by the respondents. It means that the fear of victimization had lessened due to positive police intervention, feeling safe due to the quick response of the police officers, there was a consultation and desk for crime victims in the police station, there was a specialist who gave advice and consultations for those victims of crimes, and there was a follow-up consultation from the police officers to the victim. Crime victimization can affect an individual's ability to perform in a variety of roles, including parenting, intimate relationships, and occupational and social functioning. Much of the available research focuses on changes in functioning among victims of intimate partner violence, with less attention paid to the effects of other types of crime on role functioning.

The Extent of Community Safety. The extent of community safety on police investigations in the City of Tacurong was always.

Community safety indicates that crime prevention is seen, experienced, and being done by the respondent as manifested at all times. It means that the community is safer than years ago, and the police visibility assures everyone of feeling safe in the community and satisfied with the performance of the police officers in preventing crimes in the city. Tacurong was crimes and threats city recommends that the tourists visit the city since it is safe, the police officers have the competence to decide when to use force, the police officers know how much force to use to protect the citizens, the police officers in the area treat citizens with dignity and respect, the police officers in the area were present when one needs them, and, the police officers in the area were friendly.

This is similar to a study by Mesko et al. (2018), which found that there seem to be more security-related issues in city areas, especially in urban environments, than in other municipalities. The authors based their findings on practice and research on the safety and security of European cities. The dynamics of metropolitan life are more intense, and criminal activity and other deviant behaviors are commonplace.

Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Resident's Satisfaction. When the relationship between residents' satisfaction and crime prevention was tested, the results revealed a significant correlation between the two variables. This finding indicates that higher levels of resident satisfaction with their community and local law enforcement efforts were strongly linked to more effective crime prevention outcomes. When satisfied, residents were more likely to cooperate with law enforcement by reporting suspicious activities, participating in neighborhood watch programs, and adhering to community guidelines. Moreover, satisfied residents were more likely to support and advocate for local crime prevention initiatives, such as community policing, increased funding for law enforcement resources, and public safety campaigns.

This assumption parallels the study of Cai et al. (2020), who stated that crime prevention models encompass a spectrum of approaches tailored to deter, detect, and address criminal activities. These models can be categorized into technology-oriented, target-oriented, and stage-oriented strategies, each serving distinct roles in crime prevention efforts. Technology-oriented models leverage advanced tools and systems, subdivided into punitive technologies for prosecution, corrective technologies for rehabilitation, and mechanical technologies for physical barriers. Stage-oriented models address crime at different developmental phases, targeting intention, preparation, and attempt stages through interventions such as education, monitoring, and rapid response.

Significant Relationship between Crime Prevention and Community Safety. When crime prevention and community safety were

tested, the results revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. This finding indicates that effective crime prevention measures had a substantial impact on enhancing community safety. Specifically, as crime prevention efforts increase—through strategies such as increased police patrols, community policing, public awareness campaigns, and crime deterrent technologies—there was a corresponding improvement in the overall safety and security of the community.

This assumption parallels the study of Zheng (2020), who stated that crime prevention involves strategies to improve social and physical environments to prevent, control, eliminate, and reduce criminal activities at various stages: before, during, and after crimes occur. This includes proactive measures like community education and economic opportunities, immediate interventions such as increased police presence and surveillance, and post-crime initiatives like victim support and offender rehabilitation. Criminology examines crime from etiological perspectives, focusing on the causes of criminal behavior and environmental perspectives, analyzing how physical and social settings influence crime rates. These approaches create comprehensive crime prevention programs to foster safer, more resilient communities.

Significant Relationship between Community Safety and Resident's Satisfaction. When resident satisfaction and community safety were tested, it was found that there was a significant relationship between the two variables. It indicates that residents' satisfaction significantly influences community safety. As crime prevention measures improved, there was a corresponding increase in community safety. Furthermore, the result underscores the value of community involvement in crime prevention programs, suggesting that such engagement can lead to a safer environment. Overall, the significant positive correlation underscores the critical role of effective crime prevention in enhancing community safety, providing a solid justification for continued investment and focus in this area.

This assumption parallels the study of Brewer et al., 2020 who stated that citizen satisfaction with police is crucial for fostering community buy-in and participation in addressing criminal and non-criminal matters, as it builds trust and encourages active engagement with law enforcement. When citizens are satisfied with their interactions with police, they are more likely to report crimes, share information, and participate in community initiatives, enhancing overall safety and well-being. However, predictors of citizen satisfaction have predominantly been studied in larger urban contexts, overlooking the unique dynamics of smaller or rural communities where relationships are more personal and local concerns differ.

Mediating Effect of Community Safety on the Relationship between Crime Prevention and Resident's Satisfaction. This study aimed to contribute to the literature regarding potential indirect, mediating variables for the relationship between crime prevention and resident satisfaction. In particular, community safety was investigated as a potential mediating construct to explain how crime prevention affects residents' satisfaction. While complete mediation was not found in this study, significant and critical direct effects were shown that might help enhance the existing research on crime prevention and resident satisfaction.

The mediation analysis involved the path between crime prevention and residents' satisfaction, crime prevention and community safety, and community safety and residents' satisfaction. The findings reveal significant relationships: firstly, a direct and positive association between crime prevention efforts and resident satisfaction, indicating that robust crime prevention measures contribute to greater resident contentment and security. Secondly, the analysis highlights a link between crime prevention and community safety, underscoring the role of proactive measures in reducing crime rates and enhancing overall community security. Lastly, the study identifies a mediated relationship between community safety and resident satisfaction, suggesting that perceptions of safety indirectly influence resident satisfaction, mediated by the effectiveness of crime prevention efforts.

This assumption parallels the study of Arabi et al. (2020), which established a link between crime rates and community satisfaction, suggesting that perceptions of safety and security significantly impact residents' overall quality of life. Additionally, studies have highlighted the role of crime prevention initiatives in fostering positive community outcomes, such as increased social cohesion and reduced fear of crime. Furthermore, social disorganization theory and the broken windows theory provide insights into the complex dynamics of crime, neighborhood characteristics, and resident satisfaction.

Conclusions

Based on the data gathered, the following conclusions were established: The extent of crime prevention was always in terms of crime prevention through social development, while it was seldom in terms of community crime prevention, situational crime prevention, and developmental crime prevention. Resident satisfaction was very high regarding quality of service, police-community relations, police performance, and victimization. The extent of community safety was always investigated by police in the City of Tacurong.

On the other hand, there was a significant relationship between crime prevention and community safety, resident satisfaction and community safety, and resident satisfaction and crime prevention. Moreover, crime prevention directly affected residents' satisfaction with crime prevention and community safety, as well as residents' satisfaction with police investigations.

The study's results suggest that the Philippine National Police (PNP) may prioritize improving its image by embracing a more God-fearing and service-oriented approach. Additionally, the PNP may work on strengthening its community engagement efforts through regular dialogues, town hall meetings, and community policing initiatives. This may foster trust, promote open communication, and create a collaborative approach to crime prevention. This study may also help the law enforcer enhance its role and functions by achieving peace and order. This study may also provide suggestions that help them fulfill their responsibilities to achieve peace for the

betterment of our community.

Moreover, the Filipino community, in general, may come up with a better understanding of the tasks performed towards the vision of attaining a safer place to live, work, and do business and to understand the problems encountered by them and also benefit from the study for them to be aware of the quality of service of Police Officers. Future researchers may use the study as additional reference material. Lastly, learners may use the study results to enhance their interest and research skills and help guide those who plan to conduct research relevant to the study. The study may serve as a reference material for those students who want to conduct similar or related studies. This could be guideline for those planning to conduct research relevant to the study. This may also increase students' awareness. It may also be a source for expanding knowledge in this field so they may further studies and ideas that could be applied.

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